

Evaluation of H-BEA Zeolite Dealumination and Adsorption Study of Alkylaromatics in Commercial Y-Type Zeolites

Felipe Martínez Barreto

**Undergraduate Thesis in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
for the Degree of Bachelor in:
Chemical Engineering**

Thesis Advisor:

Julio César Vargas Saenz

**UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE COLOMBIA
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING
BOGOTÁ, D.C. July 25th, 2025**

*Solo ustedes, mis pilares, mis heroínas, saben cómo ha sido este camino.
Los tres amores de mi vida, sin ustedes simplemente no estaría dónde estoy.
Gracias por impulsarme a llegar hasta aquí, por levantarme en los
momentos difíciles, por regalarme sonrisas en los más bellos, y por
motivarme siempre a seguir soñando con metas aún más grandes, no solo en
lo académico, sino en lo emocional especialmente.*

***Para mis estrellitas en el firmamento que me cuidan siempre,
está Tesis va dedicada a ustedes. Las amo...
Mamá, Dani y Sarita.***

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank my thesis advisor, Professor Julio César Vargas Saenz. This semester, under his mentorship, I learned so much—especially the deep love for knowledge and the commitment to give back to our country through teaching and academia. I hope to one day follow the same path. Thank you for your patience during the reconstruction of the reactor, and for the countless hours you dedicated to helping me understand and carry out each of the experiments.

I would also like to especially thank Professor Raj Gounder, who gave me the opportunity to begin this journey at Purdue University in West Lafayette. Thank you for trusting me, for allowing me to work in your laboratories, and for your always timely advice, which constantly motivated me to keep pursuing research. I hope to continue down that path and that our paths will cross again soon.

To my family: Rolis, Johana, and the girls. To Mamá Lucy, thank you for every time you sent me a plate of "Arrocito con Pollo". Throughout the thesis, and during my entire degree, I felt your unconditional love and support. Words are not enough to thank you.

To my university friends: Sofi, Carlos, Nakay, Brayan, and Cami. Thank you for the good times, for being there when I needed you the most, and for making "la Nacho" that magical place I always wanted to return to. Thanks to you, I'll carry with me the memory of a university filled with laughter, affection, and unforgettable moments. I wish you all the best in the new journeys ahead.

And finally, to the National University of Colombia, my alma mater, a treasure I will carry with me for the rest of my life. You taught me to love what I do, to grow as a person, and to become the human being I am today. Thank you, deeply.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	2
1. CHAPTER 1: Evaluation of H-BEA Zeolite Dealumination	10
1.1 Abstract	10
1.2 Introduction	10
1.3 Materials and Methods	13
1.3.1 H-BEA Zeolite Physicochemical Properties	13
1.3.2 H-BEA Dealumination Experimental Design	14
1.3.3 Characterization of H-BEA Dealuminated Samples	16
1.4 Results and Discussion	20
1.5 Conclusions	34
2. CHAPTER 2: Adsorption Study of Alkylaromatics in Commercial Y-Type Zeolites	36
2.1 Abstract	36
2.2 Introduction	37
2.3 Materials and Methods	38
2.3.1 Physicochemical Properties of Zeolite HY Powder (Zeolyst CBV100)	38
2.3.2 Equipment Description	39
2.3.3 Calibration of Mass Flow Controllers	44
2.3.4 TPD Experimentation Description	51
2.3.5 Mass Spectrometer Calibration	53
2.4 Results and Discussion	54
2.4.1 Mass Spectrometer Calibration Results	54
2.4.2 Adsorption/Desorption Results	57
2.5 Conclusions	67
5. REFERENCES	69
6. APPENDICES	72
A. Standard Operating Procedure's (SOP's)	72
A.1 Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) - Differential Reactor Operation	72
A.2 Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) - Adsorption/Desorption	74

B. Mass Spectrometer Calibration Results	75
B.1 Smoothed Results for Mass Spectrometer Calibration	75
B.2 Area under smoothed peaks for Mass Spectrometer Calibration	82
B.3 Results of Probe Injection Tests in the Differential Reactor: Empty and with a Bed of Ground Quartz and SiC	89
C. Saturation peaks and TPD Results	93

List of Figures

1	Dealumination Experimental Design for H-BEA (15) using EDTA and HCl	15
2	Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer (XRD) at Chemical Engineering Purdue Laboratories	16
3	Micromeritics 3-Flex instrument (N_2 adsorption) at Chemical Engineering Purdue (Gounder Group Laboratories)	17
4	Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) at Chemical Engineering Purdue (Gounder Group Laboratories)	18
5	Temperature Programmed Desorption (TPD) at Purdue Chemical Engineering (Gounder Group Laboratories)	19
6	a) Triangles - HCl, Crosses - Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13M, Diamonds - Na_2H_2EDTA 0.24M, Squares - Na_2H_2EDTA pH = 8. b) H_4EDTA	20
7	H-BEA 15 XRD Pattern (Top/Down)-([1] H-BEA 15 the lowest one/Experimental Obtained)	21
8	HCl XRD Pattern	22
9	Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 M XRD Pattern	22
10	Crystallinity Results a) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 M b) HCl	23
11	H_4EDTA XRD Pattern and Relative Crystallinity	24
12	$[H^+]/[Al]$ and $[Si]/[Al]$ for a) HCl, b) Na_2H_2EDTA at pH = 8, c) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13, d) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.24 M	25
13	HCl, Na_2H_2EDTA pH=8, Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 FAL_n/FAL_0 curves	27
14	Stacked EFAL and FAL dealumination a) HCl, b) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13M, c) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.24M	28
15	N_2 Adsorption Isotherms a) HCl, b) Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 M c) Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.24 M	29
16	Surface Area HCl	30
17	Surface Area Na_2H_2EDTA a) 0.13 M, b) 0.24M	31
18	Pore Volumen HCl	32
19	Pore Volumen Na_2H_2EDTA a) 0.13 M, b) 0.24M	33
20	Gas Phase Differential Reactor Diagram	39
21	Possible arrangement using two four-way valves	41

22	Differential Reactor and Mass Spectrometer Analysis. (a) Gas Mixer, (b) Furnace and Quartz U-tube Reactor, (c) Gas Pre-Heating Controllers, (d) Mass Flow Controllers, (e) Temperature Display of the Streams Entering the Valve Arrangement, (f) Furnace Temperature Controller, (g) QGA Mass Spectrometer. (h) Four Ways Valves Arrangement	43
23	a) Furnace-Reactor System and Packed Bed Reactor with Zeolyst CBV 712 Diluted at 4.5% in SiC (see Figure 33)	43
24	(a) Gas Mixer, (e) Temperature Display of the Streams Entering the Valve Arrangement, (f) Furnace Temperature Controller, (g) QGA Mass Spectrometer.	44
25	(c) Gas Pre-Heating Controllers, (d) Mass Flow Controllers, (h) Four Ways Valves Arrangement	44
26	Pure He Mass Flow Controller Calibration	45
27	Pure He from Gas Mixer Mass Flow Controller Calibration	46
28	Pure CO_2 from Gas Mixer Mass Flow Controller Calibration	46
29	Pure CO_2 and He Density	48
30	CO_2 - He Mixture Density using Peng-Robinson at $18^\circ C$	48
31	CO_2 - He Mixture Relative Error for lineal 5th order regression	49
32	CO_2 - He Mixture Valve opening calibration to obtain 50 mL/min at 40 PSIG	51
33	U Reactor Arrangement	52
34	Area under peaks (Blank sample) for a) Toluene and b) Benzene	55
35	Area under peaks (SiC sample) for a) Toluene and b) Benzene	55
36	Benzene concentration and Temperature Ramp Results a) $25^\circ C$, b) $75^\circ C$ and c) $150^\circ C$	57
37	Benzene TPD for Zeolite H-Y diluted in SiC	58
38	Toluene concentration and Temperature Ramp Results a) $25^\circ C$, b) $75^\circ C$ and c) $150^\circ C$	60
39	Benzene TPD for Zeolite H-Y diluted in SiC	61
40	Benzene TPD Gaussian Convolution $25^\circ C$ $n=5$	63
41	Benzene TPD Gaussian Convolution $75^\circ C$ $n=4$	63
42	Benzene TPD Gaussian Convolution $150^\circ C$ $n=3$	64
43	Toluene TPD Gaussian Convolution $25^\circ C$ $n=4$	64
44	Toluene TPD Gaussian Convolution $75^\circ C$ $n=5$	65
45	Toluene TPD Gaussian Convolution $150^\circ C$ $n=3$	65
46	Toluene and Benzene TPD reported by [2] at $25^\circ C$ as Adsorption Temperature	67

47	Smoothed Toluene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)	75
48	Smoothed Toluene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)	76
49	Smoothed Toluene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)	76
50	Smoothed Benzene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)	77
51	Smoothed Benzene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)	77
52	Smoothed Benzene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)	78
53	Smoothed Toluene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)	78
54	Smoothed Toluene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)	79
55	Smoothed Toluene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)	79
56	Smoothed Benzene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)	80
57	Smoothed Benzene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)	80
58	Smoothed Benzene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)	81
59	Area under Toluene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)	82
60	Area under Toluene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)	83
61	Area under Toluene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)	83
62	Area under Benzene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)	84
63	Area under Benzene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)	85
64	Area under Benzene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)	85
65	Area under Toluene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)	86
66	Area under Toluene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)	86
67	Area under Toluene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)	87
68	Area under Benzene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)	87
69	Area under Benzene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)	88
70	Area under Benzene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)	88
71	Area under peaks as function of Temperature in (Blank sample) a) Toluene b) Benzene	89
72	Area under peaks as function of Temperature in (SiC sample) a) Toluene b) Benzene	90
73	Area under peaks as function of Toluene 25°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC	90
74	Area under peaks as function of Toluene 75°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC	91
75	Area under peaks as function of Toluene 150°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC	91
76	Area under peaks as function of Benzene 25°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC	92
77	Area under peaks as function of Benzene 75°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC	92

78	Area under peaks as function of Benzene 150°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC	93
79	Benzene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at 25°C followed by TPD analysis.	94
80	Benzene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at 75°C followed by TPD analysis.	94
81	Benzene 25°C Adsorption TPD	95
82	Benzene 75°C Adsorption TPD	95
83	Benzene 150°C Adsorption TPD	96
84	Toluene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at 25°C followed by TPD analysis.	96
85	Toluene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at 75°C followed by TPD analysis.	97
86	Toluene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at 150°C followed by TPD analysis.	97
87	Toluene 25°C Adsorption TPD	98
88	Toluene 75°C Adsorption TPD	98
89	Toluene 150°C Adsorption TPD	99

List of Tables

1	HCl Treatment EFAL and FAL removal results	26
2	Effect of always-on HCl treatment on EFAL and FAL indicators	26
3	Surface Area HCl	31
4	Surface Area for H-BEA (15) under Na ₂ H ₂ EDTA Treatment .	32
5	Pore Volume for H-BEA (15) under HCl Treatment	33
6	Pore Volume for H-BEA (15) under Na ₂ H ₂ EDTA Treatments .	34
7	Comparison between theoretical and experimental flow rates for different CO ₂ /He mixtures	50
8	Areas under the curve for Toluene pulses at different tempera- tures and packing materials (% Alkyl Aromatic · second) . . .	54
9	Areas under the curve for Benzene pulses at different tempera- tures and packing materials (% Alkyl Aromatic · second) . . .	54
10	Fitted parameters from Gaussian convolution of Benzene TPD curves at different adsorption temperatures.	66
11	Fitted parameters from Gaussian convolution of Toluene TPD curves at different adsorption temperatures.	66

1 CHAPTER 1: Evaluation of H-BEA Zeolite Dealumination

1.1 Abstract

This chapter presents a systematic study on the dealumination of H-BEA zeolite ($\text{Si}/\text{Al} = 15$, Clariant HCZB-30) using HCl and disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetate ($\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$) at concentrations of 0.13 M and 0.24 M. The goal was to assess the ability of each agent to selectively remove extra-framework aluminum (EFAL) while preserving the framework aluminum (FAL), thus optimizing the acid site distribution and maintaining the structural integrity of the zeolite. Dealumination experiments were carried out under controlled conditions, followed by comprehensive characterization using X-ray diffraction (XRD), nitrogen physisorption, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), and ammonia temperature-programmed desorption (NH_3 -TPD).

The results show that HCl treatment leads to severe FAL extraction and crystallinity loss, evidenced by a FAL_n/FAL_0 ratio of 0.39 and minimal change in the $[\text{H}^+]/[\text{Al}]$ ratio, indicating low selectivity between EFAL and FAL removal. In contrast, $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ at 0.24 M achieved a FAL_n/FAL_0 of 0.92 and increased the $[\text{H}^+]/[\text{Al}]$ ratio from 0.62 to 0.93, corresponding to a 31% reduction in EFAL content. Similarly, the 0.13 M treatment resulted in a FAL_n/FAL_0 of 0.87 and $[\text{H}^+]/[\text{Al}]$ of 0.89. These findings confirm that disodium EDTA enables selective EFAL removal with minimal framework degradation, as corroborated by nitrogen physisorption and XRD results. Minor realumination phenomena were detected but did not significantly affect surface area or pore volume.

1.2 Introduction

Zeolites are crystalline aluminosilicate materials with an ordered microporous structure, widely used in the petrochemical industry, fine chemistry, and renewable energy applications. Their usefulness lies in their remarkable thermal stability, high specific surface area, molecular selectivity, and tunable acid-base properties. All these characteristics are closely related to their crystalline structure, which makes understanding it essential for interpreting the catalytic behavior of the material in a given reaction.

In this context, it is important to first address the formation of active sites—chemical structures that arise from the substitution of silicon atoms by aluminum atoms within the tetrahedral SiO_4 network. This substitution generates a charge imbalance in the framework, which must be compensated by incorporating a metal complex, a metal cation, or a Brønsted acid proton (H^+). This chemical arrangement leads to a well-defined porous crystalline structure with surface catalytic activity, as well as a complex network of interconnected channels between the pores.

Aluminum can naturally be found within the framework structure (framework aluminum, FAL), but it may also appear as species located on the inner pore surfaces, known as extra-framework aluminum (EFAL). These EFAL species can block active sites, reducing catalytic efficiency, or form Lewis acid sites that may trigger undesired side reactions through the generation of intermediates.

Therefore, the selective removal of EFAL species may enhance the efficiency of specific reactions within the zeolite structure. In this regard, various authors have proposed treatments and analytical strategies to eliminate these aluminum species.

As [3] report, the dealumination of Beta zeolite using HCl and EDTA treatments allows for fine-tuning of its structural and acid-base properties, thereby optimizing its performance as a catalyst in the oligomerization of isobutanol toward jet fuel-range hydrocarbons. HCl treatment removes both EFAL and part of the FAL, which decreases the number of Brønsted acid sites but increases the relative proportion of Lewis acid sites, favoring oligomerization. In contrast, EDTA acts more selectively, removing mainly EFAL while largely preserving FAL, thus maintaining a higher proportion of Brønsted acid sites. This difference translates into catalytic behavior: while the HCl2h-BEA catalyst reached a 98% conversion and 59% selectivity to C8–C16 products, the EDTA8h-BEA catalyst achieved a 91% conversion and 53% selectivity. These results show that it is possible to control the distribution between FAl and EFAl species, as well as the degree of crystalline degradation, depending on the type and interaction strength of the dealuminating agent with the zeolite.

On the other hand, [4] indicate that dealumination of small-pore zeolites by acid treatment, combined with structural stabilization from organic cations within the pores, enables a controlled adjustment of the Si/Al ratio without drastically compromising the crystallinity of the material. In their study with AFX zeolite, the initial crystallinity was preserved following the removal of FAL and the formation of extra-framework aluminum species EFAL; however, in later stages of treatment, a transient increase in crystallinity was observed, followed by a significant decrease. This phenomenon was attributed to the partial reincorporation of EFAL species into the framework, leading to a local reorganization of the network that, while potentially stabilizing certain defects, also caused distortions negatively affecting overall crystallinity. This behavior was confirmed by Al NMR spectroscopy, which revealed the migration of aluminum species from extra-framework to tetrahedral positions, and by changes in X-Ray diffraction patterns. The study demonstrates that precise control of the dealumination process, followed by a defect-curing step, not only modulates the acidity and composition of the material but also its dynamic structural stability, in which aluminum reincorporation may play a dual role—either stabilizing or disruptive—depending on the balance between removal and healing.

Considering the previous literature review and the strong industrial interest in the selective removal of EFAL, the present chapter proposes the study of the dealumination of Clariant's H-BEA zeolite (HCZB-30) with a Si/Al ratio of 15, using HCl and EDTA (in both tetraacid and disodium forms), with time as the variable at a fixed temperature. According to the literature, it is expected that the strong acid will have greater capacity to remove FAl from the structure, while disodium EDTA will not. X-Ray diffraction (XRD), nitrogen adsorption, temperature-programmed desorption (TPD), and ICP analysis were used to monitor the crystallinity, surface characteristics and pore size, Brønsted acid sites, and elemental composition of silicon and aluminum.

1.3 Materials and Methods

1.3.1 H-BEA Zeolite Physicochemical Properties

H-BEA (Beta) zeolite is a high-silica, three-dimensional microporous aluminosilicate with a large pore system, widely employed in catalytic and adsorption processes due to its favorable textural and acidic characteristics. Structurally, H-BEA belongs to the BEA topology (Framework Type Code: *BEA*), which consists of a three-dimensional network of 12-membered ring channels with pore openings of approximately $6.6 \text{ \AA} \times 6.7 \text{ \AA}$ [5]. This architecture provides relatively large pore volumes and accessible internal surface areas, enabling the diffusion and transformation of bulky molecules, particularly in liquid-phase reactions.

The framework of H-BEA is composed of corner-sharing SiO_4 and AlO_4 tetrahedra. The substitution of Si^{4+} by Al^{3+} introduces negative framework charges that are compensated by extraframework cations. In the protonic form (H-BEA), these are protons (H^+), giving rise to Brønsted acid sites that are critical for acid-catalyzed reactions. The density and strength of these acid sites depend heavily on the Si/Al ratio, which typically ranges from 12 to over 100, with higher ratios resulting in lower acidity but increased hydrophobicity and thermal stability [6, 7].

H-BEA zeolites exhibit high surface areas, generally between 500 and 700 m^2/g , and total pore volumes ranging from 0.3 to 0.5 cm^3/g , as measured by nitrogen physisorption (BET and BJH methods) [8]. These textural properties, combined with thermal stability exceeding 750 $^\circ\text{C}$, allow the use of H-BEA in demanding catalytic and adsorption conditions [9]. Due to their relatively weak hydrophilicity at high Si/Al ratios, H-BEA zeolites perform well in the presence of nonpolar molecules and under mild aqueous conditions.

Crystallographically, H-BEA is composed of intergrown polymorphs (A and B), which introduce a certain degree of disorder but maintain the pore connectivity and accessibility [5]. The synthesis of BEA-type zeolites generally involves a hydrothermal process using tetraethylammonium hydroxide (TEAOH) as the organic structure-directing agent (OSDA), followed by calcination to remove the template and obtain the protonic form [7, 10].

In summary, H-BEA combines large pore size, high surface area, thermal

robustness, and tunable Brønsted acidity, making it an excellent candidate for applications in catalysis and adsorption, especially for transformations involving aromatic hydrocarbons and other bulky organic molecules [6].

1.3.2 H-BEA Dealumination Experimental Design

Based on the study by [3], further investigation was carried out on how post-synthesis treatments can modify the H-BEA framework using substances with varying acid strengths, particularly for the removal of EFAL. This Al-type structures have been reported to negatively affect oligomerization reactions by blocking the internal channels of the zeolite. With the mentioned treatment, zeolite pores become smoother, as EFAL and certain impurities can be effectively removed, as noted in the reference study.

However, the removal of aluminum species can partially degrade the crystal structure, depending on the interaction between the acid and the zeolite framework. In the case of HCl, this interaction appears to be stronger, making the removal process more abrupt and aggressive over time, whereas that of EDTA exhibits a milder effect.

These observations prompt further investigation into the combined influence of treatment time and acid concentration on the stability and composition of the zeolite framework, particularly regarding whether there is a preferential removal of extra-framework aluminum (EFAL) versus framework aluminum (FAL), and how these variables control such selectivity over time. This behavior is proposed as a central focus and a novel contribution of this thesis. Moreover, due to limitations related to the reflux system and the low solubility of anhydrous EDTA in water, the disodium salt form of EDTA was employed, opening a new line of research into the interaction of different EDTA species with the zeolite framework.

In light of these considerations, four dealumination experiments were conducted using H-BEA zeolite. The first involved treatment with 1 M HCl at 80°C for 15, 30, 60, and 120 minutes, with the aim of reproducing the results reported by [3]. The second experiment utilized 0.5 M EDTA in a basic solution (pH = 8) for 1, 2, 4, and 8 hours at 100°C. In the third, tetrasodium EDTA was applied at a concentration of 0.5 g/L for durations

of 1 and 24 hours at 100°C. Finally, aqueous solutions of disodium EDTA were prepared at concentrations of 0.13 and 0.24 M and applied for 1, 2, 4, and 8 hours at 100°C.

In general terms, the experimental design follows the scheme shown in **Figure 1**, starting with H-BEA (15) zeolite supplied by Clariant (HCZB-30). Approximately 2.0000 ± 0.0001 grams of sample were taken for dealumination and 20 ml of the corresponding acid solution was added to a Teflon vessel. The acid treatment was then carried out at 100°C for the durations mentioned previously for each acid. After the dealumination step, the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm and washed five times with DI water to remove the supernatant. Finally, the solids were left in a static oven at 373 K overnight.

Figure 1: Dealumination Experimental Design for H-BEA (15) using EDTA and HCl

With the sample dried and placed in the vials, morphological analyzes of the dealuminated structures were carried out using XRD, N₂ adsorption, ICP, and TPD techniques to determine surface and volumetric properties, such as specific surface area and total, external, and micropore volume, as well as the BJH pore size distribution. In addition, XRD patterns were

analyzed to assess whether any destruction of the crystalline structure had occurred after treatment. Furthermore, the amount of acid sites [FAL] and the Si/Al ratio of the structure were measured to enable a deeper analysis of the studied phenomenon. The following sections describe each of the techniques in more detail.

1.3.3 Characterization of H-BEA Dealuminated Samples

- **XRD**

The crystal structures were analyzed by obtaining powder X-ray diffraction data using a Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer equipped with a Cu $K\alpha$ radiation source ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$, operating conditions: 40 kV and 44 mA). Diffraction measurements were performed over a 2θ range of 4° to 50° with a step of 0.01° and a scanning rate of 0.0167° per second. The equipment can be seen in **Figure 2**:

Figure 2: Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer (XRD) at Chemical Engineering Purdue Laboratories

- **N₂ Adsorption**

Nitrogen adsorption isotherms were acquired at 77 K using a Micromeritics 3-Flex instrument. Approximately 0.05 g of sample was first degassed under a dynamic vacuum (pressure below 0.67 kPa), then heated at 393 K for 2 hours followed by further heating at 623 K for 9 hours with a controlled rate of 0.167 K per second before conducting the adsorption experiments. 3-Flex equipment can be seen in **Figure 3**:

Figure 3: Micromeritics 3-Flex instrument (N_2 adsorption) at Chemical Engineering Purdue (Gounder Group Laboratories)

- **ICP-OES**

For elemental analysis, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was used, employing a Thermo Scientific iCAP 7000 Plus Series instrument as it may be seen in **Figure 4**. For

this purpose, about 0.02 g of the solid sample was dissolved in 2.5 g of hydrofluoric acid (48 wt %, Alfa Aesar). After allowing the reaction to proceed for over 24 hours, 1 g of nitric acid (70 wt %, Sigma-Aldrich) was added, and the solution was further diluted with 50 g of deionized water.

Figure 4: Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) at Chemical Engineering Purdue (Gounder Group Laboratories)

- **TPD**

Ammonia temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) was carried out to determine the quantity of protonic (H^+) sites present on BEA zeolite samples. Prior to the TPD analysis, the samples underwent an ion-exchange procedure using ammonium nitrate to replace sodium or other

exchangeable cations with ammonium ions. For each run, between 0.02 and 0.06 grams of sample were packed into a quartz U-tube reactor and held in place with quartz wool on both ends. The TPD measurements were conducted using a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 Chemisorption Analyzer seen in **Figure 5**. After ion exchange, the samples were subjected to a temperature ramp under helium flow to thermally decompose the ammonium ions, leading to the desorption of ammonia and allowing quantification of the Brønsted acid sites present in the material.

Figure 5: Temperature Programmed Desorption (TPD) at Purdue Chemical Engineering (Gounder Group Laboratories)

1.4 Results and Discussion

The first analysis obtained, which provides the clearest overview of the dealumination process for each of the species, was the elemental analysis by ICP. Based on the methodology described previously, it was possible to calculate the amount of Si and Al in %wt, and from this estimate the [Si/Al] ratio for each of the aforementioned species as a function of time, as shown in the following **Figure 6**:

Figure 6: a) Triangles - HCl, Crosses - Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13M, Diamonds - Na_2H_2EDTA 0.24M, Squares - Na_2H_2EDTA pH = 8. b) H_4EDTA

Furthermore, it was found that there is no significant change in the Si wt% of the dealuminated samples, as also reported by [3] in their results. This observation will become even more relevant in a later analysis. However, in the case of Al wt%, a noticeable decrease was observed, which is reflected in a progressive increase in the [Si/Al] ratio for each of the species.

In the case of HCl, it is evident that the dealumination process is stronger than that observed with the three different EDTA forms evaluated. Notably, the [Si/Al] ratio does not converge to a stable value, which may indicate that this particular treatment removes both (FAL) and (EFAL) throughout the dealumination process. In contrast, for all EDTA-based treatments, the removal of aluminum appears to stabilize, suggesting a preference for extracting the more easily accessible structures, EFAL, until it reaches a point where further removal is no longer possible. This behavior implies

that, unlike HCl, EDTA is not capable of extracting structural aluminum from the zeolite framework. Later, it will be confirmed or not by analyzing the TPD results.

Finally, in terms of the ICP results, it is worth noting that compared to H_4EDTA and Na_2H_2EDTA at $pH = 8$ treatments, Na_2H_2EDTA solutions at concentrations of 0.13 and 0.24 M are more effective at removing aluminum, reaching $[Si/Al]$ values of up to 28. This suggests that treatment with H_4EDTA and Na_2H_2EDTA at $pH = 8$ does not possess enough acidity to remove any form of EFAL. For this reason, they will not be discussed in detail in the future, unlike HCl and Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M, which will remain the focus.

On the basis of the previous analysis, the next technique to further complement the understanding of the dealumination process was the study of crystallinity through XRD. Initially, special attention was given to the patterns of HCl and Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M, as these are the conditions that, up to this point, appear to have induced significant structural changes. First, the XRD pattern was compared with the literature reported in [1], as it may be seen in **Figure 7**:

Figure 7: H-BEA 15 XRD Pattern (Top/Down)-([1] H-BEA 15 the lowest one/Experimental Obtained)

As can be observed, the reference zeolite exhibits the same characteristic peaks reported by [1] for H-BEA (15) zeolites, specifically within the ranges of 7-8° and 22-23°. Taking this into account, the following **Figure 8** and **Figure 9** compare this reference pattern as the baseline in all diagrams with the dealuminated samples, initially for HCl and Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M for each treatment time:

Figure 8: HCl XRD Pattern

Figure 9: Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 M XRD Pattern

At first glance, no significant changes are observed in the patterns, meaning there is no evidence of a total degradation of the structure. For this reason, the calculation of Relative Crystallinity with respect to the

reference pattern is carried out in order to perform a more detailed analysis of the changes in the crystalline structure as a function of the acid used and the treatment time. The following presents the expression used for the Crystallinity calculation and the corresponding results:

$$C_{Rel} = \frac{\sum \bar{I}_{Sample}}{\sum \bar{I}_{Pattern}} \quad (1)$$

The summation was performed for the characteristic peaks located at 7 to 8 ° and 22 to 23 °, resulting in the following:

Figure 10: Crystallinity Results a) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 M b) HCl

In **Figure 10**, a similar behavior can be observed in all treatments, showing an initial increase in crystallinity followed by a decline. This can be complemented by the observations in [4], where an initial removal of EFAL located in the micropores leads to pore opening. However, as time progresses, the interaction with FAL becomes more frequent. Up to this point, based on the results obtained, this reasoning appears to be consistent with the findings. Nevertheless, data from TPD analysis presented later will demonstrate a novel effect that supports this preferential removal behavior throughout the dealumination process.

Finally, XRD and crystallinity results were obtained for H_4EDTA , confirming—along with the ICP results in **Figure 6**—that no significant dealumination occurred. The same conclusion applies to Na_2H_2EDTA at

pH = 8.

Figure 11: H_4EDTA XRD Pattern and Relative Crystallinity

Now, the complementary analysis to ICP for this experimentation was TPD, which allows determining the number of Brnsted acid sites associated with an FAL, through ion exchange with NH_4NO_3 followed by ammonia desorption using a programmed temperature ramp and an online chromatograph in AutoChem. This means that, from the total aluminum content estimated by ICP, it is now possible to distinguish between FAL and EFAL, allowing the estimation of the $\frac{[H^+]}{Al}$ ratio. With this, the following graphs were constructed:

Figure 12: $[H^+]/[Al]$ and $[Si]/[Al]$ for a) HCl, b) Na_2H_2EDTA at pH = 8, c) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13, d) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.24 M

For the following analysis, it is important to take into account $\frac{[H^+]}{[Al]}$ and $\frac{[Si]}{[Al]}$ mathematical definitions in terms of EFAL and FAL just to obtain a novel approach for dealumination process:

$$\left[\frac{Si}{Al} \right] = \frac{[Si]}{[FAL] + [EFAL]} \quad (2)$$

$$\left[\frac{H^+}{Al} \right] = \frac{[FAL]}{[FAL] + [EFAL]} \quad (3)$$

From **Equations 2** and **3**, and summarizing the results from **Figure 12**, the following was obtained for HCl:

Table 1: HCl Treatment EFAL and FAL removal results

Time (min)	$[H^+/Al]$	$[Si/Al]$	$[EFAL] + [FAL]$	$[FAL]$	$[EFAL]$ Loss rate
< 30	↑	↑	↑	> $[EFAL] + [FAL]$	↑
> 30	↓	↓	↓	< $[EFAL] + [FAL]$	↓

Using upward arrows to indicate an increase and downward arrows to indicate a decrease for each time interval. From the $\frac{[H^+]}{Al}$ and $\frac{[Si]}{Al}$ boxes and **Equations 2** and **3**, and considering that the $[Si]$ content determined by ICP is assumed not to vary significantly, the increase in $\frac{[Si]}{Al}$ only indicates that the total aluminum content is decreasing. This, together with the increase in $\frac{[H^+]}{Al}$, can only imply that the decrease in the sum of EFAL and FAL is more significant than that of FAL alone, and therefore, the loss rate of EFAL during the first 30 minutes for HCl is greater than that of FAL. However, after 30 minutes, despite the continued loss of total aluminum, the $\frac{[H^+]}{Al}$ ratio drops, implying that, mathematically speaking, FAL must then have a higher loss rate. This behavior is consistent with what has been reported in the literature in [4].

In the case of Na_2H_2EDTA at pH = 8, since no significant change was observed in the $\frac{[Si]}{Al}$ ratio, this analysis was inconclusive. On the other hand, for Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M, the following results were obtained under the same analysis:

Table 2: Effect of always-on HCl treatment on EFAL and FAL indicators

Time (min)	$[H^+/Al]$	$[Si/Al]$	$[EFAL] + [FAL]$	$[FAL]$	$[EFAL]$ Loss rate
Always	↑	↑	↓	> $[EFAL] + [FAL]$	↑

From the previous result for Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M, the same trend observed for HCl can be seen before the first 30 minutes, that is, a higher loss rate of EFAL compared to FAL. However, for Na_2H_2EDTA at both concentrations, this behavior is maintained throughout the interval. This indicates that, being a weaker acid, it preferentially interacts with EFAL for its removal rather than with FAL. In the case of HCl, this initially occurs as a selective removal of EFAL, but after a certain removal time, the acid begins to extract FAL at a higher rate because it is a stronger acid and

therefore has a greater capacity to interact with the crystalline structure.

However, using the concentration of FAL sites obtained from the TPD data, a corresponding monitoring of these sites was carried out over the dealumination time with respect to the initial FAL content in the sample:

Figure 13: HCl, Na_2H_2EDTA pH=8, Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 FAL_n/FAL_0 curves

From **Figure 13**, obtained from the combined ICP and TPD results, the trend previously discussed in **Tables 1** and **2** is confirmed. In the case of HCl, there is a continuous decrease over time. For Na_2H_2EDTA at pH = 8, it is once again confirmed that there is no significant effect on FAL or EFAL. However, for Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M, a decreasing trend is observed, followed by an increase between 1 and 2 hours. This behavior can be explained by a realumination phenomenon, which is common in BEA-type zeolites when the pH of the solution is kept below 7, as reported in [11].

In other words, part of the aluminum that is removed from the pores can be reincorporated into the framework. However, based on the XRD results in **Figures 8** and **11**, this reincorporation appears to be disordered. This is suggested by the decrease in relative crystallinity after 30 minutes for HCl and after 1 to 2 hours for Na_2H_2EDTA , despite partial reincorporation of aluminum - considering that 10 to 15% of the initial FAL is removed at the end of treatment.

Finally, this section presents stacked plots of FAL and EFAL to complete the analysis of the ICP and TPD results.

Figure 14: Stacked EFAL and FAL dealumination a) HCl, b) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13M, c) Na_2H_2EDTA 0.24M

In **Figure 14**, the behavior previously mentioned is clearly illustrated. For HCl, both aluminum species decrease significantly. In contrast, for Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 M and 0.24 M, a preferential dealumination of EFAL is observed, along with a reincorporation of aluminum into the structure after 2 hours. Now, Nitrogen Adsorption will support the previous results:

Figure 15: N_2 Adsorption Isotherms a) HCl, b) Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 M c) Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.24 M

Based on the nitrogen adsorption isotherms shown in **Figure 15**, a clear influence of the chemical treatment on the porosity of the material can be observed. All curves exhibit characteristics of type IV isotherms with hysteresis loops, confirming the presence of mesopores. In the upper panel, corresponding to the HCl treatment, a progressive decrease in the adsorbed volume is evident with increasing treatment time, suggesting severe dealumination and a possible partial collapse of the mesoporous structure.

In contrast, the bottom panels show the results for Na_2H_2EDTA treatments at different concentrations (0.13 M on the left and 0.24 M on the right). In these cases, although a decrease in the adsorbed volume is also observed in the initial stages, a slight recovery occurs after 2 hours, especially in the 0.24 M condition. This behavior may indicate a more selective removal of EFAL and a partial reintegration or reorganization of aluminum into the structure, preserving mesoporosity without causing significant structural collapse. Overall, EDTA treatments appear to maintain the structural integrity of the material better compared to that obtained with strong acid treatment.

However, regarding the surface area, it can be observed that for HCl, there is an initial removal of aluminum obstructing the micropores during the first 15 minutes, which results in a slight increase in surface area. Nevertheless, as time progresses, aluminum begins to be removed from both framework and extraframework structures at a similar rate.

Figure 16: Surface Area HCl

Table 3: Surface Area HCl

Sample	Time (h)	Surface Area (m ² /g)		
		Total	Micropore	External
Parent-HBEA (15) HCZ30	0	618	468	151
H-BEA (15) HCl	0.25	643	449	194
	0.5	592	417	175
	1	549	379	169
	2	566	400	156

For its part, the surface treated with Na_2H_2EDTA does not seem to show a significant change in the surface area, both for micropores and external sites of the crystalline structure, as can be seen in **Figure 17**:

Figure 17: Surface Area Na_2H_2EDTA a) 0.13 M, b) 0.24M

Table 4: Surface Area for H-BEA (15) under Na₂H₂EDTA Treatment

Sample	Time (h)	Surface Area (m ² /g)		
		Total	Micropore	External
Parent-HBEA (15) HCZ30	0	618	468	151
H-BEA(15) Na ₂ H ₂ EDTA 0.13M	1	614	444	169
	2	620	444	175
	8	605	435	170
H-BEA(15) Na ₂ H ₂ EDTA 0.13M	1	603	432	172
	2	614	438	176
	8	591	420	171

Just as with the surface area, an initial increase in pore volume can be observed, associated with the effect of aluminum removal that was blocking the pores. However, as in the previous case, when the structure degrades, the volume of each type of pore also decreases, as shown in **Figure 18**:

Figure 18: Pore Volumen HCl

Table 5: Pore Volume for H-BEA (15) under HCl Treatment

Sample	Time (h)	Pore Volume (m ³ /g)		
		Total	Micropore	External
Parent-HBEA (15) HCZ30	0	0.369	0.244	0.125
H-BEA (15) HCl	0.25	0.395	0.236	0.159
	0.5	0.363	0.231	0.132
	1	0.337	0.196	0.141
	2	0.335	0.213	0.122

For the pore volume of the Na_2H_2EDTA -treated sample, there was also no significant change, which is desirable for the dealumination process, as shown in **Figure 19**:

Figure 19: Pore Volumen Na_2H_2EDTA a) 0.13 M, b) 0.24M

Table 6: Pore Volume for H-BEA (15) under $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ Treatments

Sample	Time (h)	Pore Volume (m^3/g)		
		Total	Micropore	External
Parent-HBEA (15) HCZ30	0	0.369	0.244	0.125
H-BEA(15) $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ 0.13M	1	0.378	0.222	0.157
	2	0.383	0.219	0.164
	8	0.375	0.218	0.157
H-BEA(15) $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ 0.24M	1	0.371	0.225	0.146
	2	0.375	0.217	0.158
	8	0.367	0.209	0.158

1.5 Conclusions

Based on the results obtained using the various previously described techniques, it was found that the dealuminating agents with the most significant effects were HCl and $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ at concentrations of 0.13 and 0.24 M. In contrast, the basic and anhydrous forms of EDTA produced no observable structural or physicochemical changes on the surface. Notably, the most effective dealumination was achieved with $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ 0.24 M after 8 hours, reaching a FAL_n/FAL_0 ratio of 0.92, which corresponds to an 8% loss of framework aluminum (FAL) compared to the reference material. Additionally, the $[H^+/\text{Al}]$ ratio increased from 0.62 to 0.93, indicating a decrease in the extra-framework aluminum (EFAL) population from 38% to 7%, i.e., a 31% reduction relative to the initial value.

The second-best performance was observed with $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{EDTA}$ 0.13 M, showing a FAL_n/FAL_0 ratio of 0.87 after 8 hours, equivalent to a 13% loss of FAL, and an increase in the $[H^+/\text{Al}]$ ratio from 0.62 to 0.89, corresponding to a 27% reduction in EFAL content.

In contrast, the HCl treatment resulted in an undesired effect, with a FAL_n/FAL_0 ratio dropping to 0.39 after just 2 hours, indicating excessive removal of FAL. Moreover, the $[H^+/\text{Al}]$ ratio increased only slightly, from 0.62 to 0.65, suggesting that no clear selectivity was achieved between EFAL

and FAL removal. **Figure 14** clearly illustrates this behavior.

Furthermore, combined ICP and TPD analysis revealed partial reincorporation of EFAL into the framework as FAL in the samples treated with Na_2H_2EDTA 0.13 and 0.24 M. This phenomenon is observed in **Figure 14** as an increase in the slope of framework aluminum content and also in **Figure 13** through the evolution of the FAL_n/FAL_0 ratio. However, based on XRD results, this reincorporation does not appear to preserve the crystallinity of the original structure.

A time-dependent trend in the removal rates of EFAL and FAL was also identified, as seen in **Figure 12**. Initially, HCl treatment removes primarily EFAL, which is reflected in the 3-Flex analysis as an increase in external pore volume (micropore opening). However, after a certain point, the trend shifts toward predominant removal of FAL, resulting in a gradual decrease in both surface area and pore volume. In contrast, Na_2H_2EDTA treatments at 0.13 and 0.24 M selectively remove EFAL throughout the entire time range studied, with negligible changes in surface and porosity properties.

In conclusion, treatment of H-BEA zeolite ($Si/Al = 15$) with Na_2H_2EDTA at 0.13 and 0.24 M allows for selective removal of EFAL species, achieving $[H^+/Al]$ ratios of 0.89 and 0.93, respectively, with controlled losses of FAL (13% and 8%). These modifications were accomplished without significant changes in key properties such as surface area, pore volume, or relative crystallinity compared to the reference material.

For future research, it would be valuable to understand, at a molecular level, the interactions between Na_2H_2EDTA and the different forms of EFAL and FAL, to investigate how EFAL reincorporation may be influenced by diffusion limitations, and to explore how the reduced acidity of EDTA—due to sodium counterions—affects dealumination efficiency. Further studies on zeolites with narrower pore systems are also encouraged.

2 CHAPTER 2: Adsorption Study of Alkylaromatics in Commercial Y-Type Zeolites

2.1 Abstract

The adsorption and desorption behavior of alkyl aromatic compounds on H-Y CBV 100 zeolite was investigated using temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) experiments with toluene and benzene as probe molecules. The study aimed to evaluate the influence of adsorption temperature and bed configuration on desorption profiles, focusing on diffusion limitations within the porous zeolite network. A diluted bed using SiC was employed to minimize transport artifacts, allowing a clearer distinction of adsorption site distributions and energetic profiles.

Results showed distinct differences between the desorption behaviors of benzene and toluene. Benzene exhibited sharper, well-defined peaks without shoulders, indicating less hindered desorption, while toluene showed broader peaks with pseudo-peaks (shoulders), particularly at lower adsorption temperatures (25°C and 75°C), reflecting stronger diffusional constraints. Increasing the adsorption temperature led to a shift of desorption peaks toward lower temperatures and a notable reduction in peak intensity, attributed to reduced molecular loading and weaker cooperative interactions. In the case of benzene, additional high-temperature peaks were observed at elevated adsorption temperatures, likely due to enhanced access to micropores by more mobile, high-energy molecules.

A qualitative analysis of the number and distribution of adsorption sites was performed by fitting the TPD data using a Gaussian convolution approach with the `lsqcurvefit` optimization function in MATLAB. While this method provided insight into the dominant desorption sites, it remains a phenomenological approximation. Comparative analysis with a previous study using undiluted beds [2] confirmed the positive impact of SiC dilution in minimizing diffusional resistance and enhancing the interpretability of desorption behavior in zeolite systems.

2.2 Introduction

The study of adsorption and desorption phenomena in porous materials has been widely investigated due to its importance in separation processes, storage systems, and heterogeneous catalysis. In particular, Y-type zeolites, owing to their well-defined crystalline structure and the presence of Brønsted acid sites, have been extensively used in studies focusing on the interaction of organic and inorganic molecules with microporous surfaces. However, due to the complexity of their pore network, mass transport within these structures is often limited by intracrystalline or interparticle diffusion phenomena, which can significantly affect the experimentally observed adsorption and desorption profiles.

Several studies have highlighted how diffusive transport can distort the data obtained through techniques such as temperature-programmed desorption (TPD). For instance, the introduction of meso- and macroporosity in hierarchical zeolites has been shown to enhance molecular mobility and reduce the distortion of TPD profiles [12]. Likewise, diffusion inside microporous frameworks can lead to broadened peaks or multiple desorption signals in TPD curves, which are often associated with a distribution of adsorption energies and internal transport barriers [13, 14]. Additional work has emphasized how bed compaction, porosity, and crystal size affect the desorption kinetics of aromatic compounds, introducing thermal hysteresis and diffusional delay effects [15].

In line with this research, a previous study focused on the desorption behavior of toluene and benzene in H-Y CBV 100 zeolite using TPD analysis [2]. The resulting desorption profiles exhibited broad peaks, high-temperature shifts, and the presence of shoulder-like features, all of which suggest internal diffusion limitations and a heterogeneous distribution of active sites. The use of a compact bed in that study revealed the influence of transport phenomena superimposed on the energetic behavior of the adsorbate–adsorbent system.

Other investigations have explored strategies to reduce transport effects by modifying bed architecture. Dilution of the zeolite phase with inert materials such as SiC has been shown to improve thermal uniformity and facilitate desorption by reducing the resistance to bulk flow and internal diffusion [16]. Moreover, the development of mesostructured zeolites with

enhanced pore accessibility and shorter diffusion paths has further enabled the generation of sharper and more interpretable TPD peaks [17].

Within this framework, the present chapter presents a comparative analysis of the TPD results for benzene and toluene adsorbed on H-Y CBV 100 zeolite using a bed diluted with SiC, as opposed to conventional configurations such as that employed in [2]. The objective is to assess how adsorption temperature and bed structure influence the emergence of diffusive phenomena, and how these, in turn, affect the qualitative interpretation of adsorption energetics and the distribution of active sites within the zeolite.

2.3 Materials and Methods

2.3.1 Physicochemical Properties of Zeolite HY Powder (Zeolyst CBV100)

Zeolyst CBV100 is a commercially available HY-type zeolite (NaY) synthesized as a fine white powder, odorless and insoluble, intended for adsorption and catalytic applications [18]. It possesses a faujasite (FAU) framework, characterized by a three-dimensional network of supercages (13\AA) interconnected via 12-membered ring windows (7.4\AA), which enables access for relatively large molecules [19, 20].

The material typically exhibits a Si/Al molar ratio around 5–5.1, providing strong Brønsted acidity associated with framework aluminum sites, making HY zeolites highly active in acid-catalyzed reactions [21, 22]. The surface area is high ($900\text{m}^2/\text{g}$) with significant micropore and total pore volume, although external surface area remains low [21, 23].

CBV100 is utilized extensively in catalytic cracking processes due to its strong acidity and thermal stability. It is also effective in polymer degradation studies, where its strong acid sites accelerate the onset of cracking reactions [22]. Additionally, its structure allows for applications in ionic separations and molecular sieving [24].

Upon dealumination (e.g., via steaming or acid treatments), CBV100 can be converted to HY or H-USY forms, enhancing hydrothermal stability and generating mesoporosity that improves catalytic lifetime and access to active sites [20, 17]. In NO_x reduction, copper-loaded CBV100 has demonstrated stable catalytic performance above 300°C in flue-gas conditions [25].

2.3.2 Equipment Description

Based on the Master's thesis by Cindy Ly Tavera [2], the equipment used for her adsorption tests of alkyl aromatics on commercial zeolites was reassembled, as it had been out of operation since 2022. The setup of this system is shown in **Figure 20**.

Figure 20: Gas Phase Differential Reactor Diagram

The system can be better understood by first providing an overview of the equipment. At its core, the setup centers around a Differential Reactor, consisting of a quartz U-tube enclosed within a furnace. The furnace supplies the necessary energy to maintain a constant temperature or to follow a programmed temperature ramp, regulated precisely by a temperature controller.

To achieve better control over the reaction or adsorption rate, a slight dilution of the feed was essential. For this purpose, two gas inlets were connected: one for a mixed gas stream such like Helium (He), Argon (Ar), Hydrogen (H_2), Oxygen (O_2), Methane (CH_4), Carbon Dioxide (CO_2) or Nitrogen (N_2) and the other for a pure gas flow. The mixed gas line is fed by

a gas mixer composed of several Mass Flow Controllers (MFCs), while the second line supplies pure helium or argon directly. The specific use of each gas stream during the experimental procedure will be discussed later.

Each of the gas inlet lines is equipped with a temperature controller, a heating tape, and a thermocouple. This configuration allows for precise temperature control during the gas preheating stage, ensuring that the desired temperature is reached inside the reactor under steady-state conditions.

Both lines will independently enter an arrangement of two four-way valves (diverter valves), which will allow for different configurations depending on the specific case, as shown below in **Figure 21**:

Figure 21: Possible arrangement using two four-way valves

The first configuration shown in **Figure 21** allows the He/Ar stream to flow directly into the reactor and then exit straight to the atmosphere, while the gas mixture from the mixing box flows from valve V1 to V2 and then to the QGA. This setup is useful when it is necessary to verify the composition of the mixture coming from the mixing box while simultaneously removing water from the zeolite.

In the second configuration, only the orientation of valve V2 is changed, which alters the direction of the incoming gas streams. In this case, the He/Ar gas exiting the reactor is directed to the QGA for analysis, while the gas from the mixing box is vented to the atmosphere. This specific configuration is used to quantify the amount of the probe injected (see injection point in **Figure 20**) that has not been adsorbed by the zeolite. Meanwhile, the gas from the mixing box is vented. This is a typical configuration often used after the fourth configuration, in which dry air is used to calcine the zeolite, followed by a switch to configuration 2 to inject pulses and initiate the TPD experiments.

The third configuration, like the first, allows the gas passing through the reactor to be vented to the atmosphere—this time, the gas coming from the mixing box—while the He/Ar stream is directed to the QGA. This setup is used once water has been completely removed from the system, and a continuous flow of He/Ar is sent to the QGA, which must never be left without a gas stream at any point.

Finally, the fourth configuration, as previously mentioned, is used during the calcination stage, which will be discussed in more detail later. In this configuration, a flow of dry air is passed through the reactor to remove any traces of contaminants or water, which are analyzed in the QGA to enable a quantitative assessment during the calcination period. Meanwhile, the He/Ar from the direct line which will later be directed to the reactor for the TPD experiments is vented to the atmosphere.

The following photographs show the experimental setup in the Instrumental 1 laboratory at the National University of Colombia:

Figure 22: Differential Reactor and Mass Spectrometer Analysis. (a) Gas Mixer, (b) Furnace and Quartz U-tube Reactor, (c) Gas Pre-Heating Controllers, (d) Mass Flow Controllers, (e) Temperature Display of the Streams Entering the Valve Arrangement, (f) Furnace Temperature Controller, (g) QGA Mass Spectrometer. (h) Four Ways Valves Arrangement

Figure 23: a) Furnace-Reactor System and Packed Bed Reactor with Zeolyst CBV 712 Diluted at 4.5% in SiC (see Figure 33)

Figure 24: (a) Gas Mixer, (e) Temperature Display of the Streams Entering the Valve Arrangement, (f) Furnace Temperature Controller, (g) QGA Mass Spectrometer.

Figure 25: (c) Gas Pre-Heating Controllers, (d) Mass Flow Controllers, (h) Four Ways Valves Arrangement

2.3.3 Calibration of Mass Flow Controllers

Since the system is still under development, and given the time constraints and scope of this undergraduate thesis, calibrations were carried out only for the pure helium line and for pure helium passing through the mixing

box and Air. Furthermore, as the next project to be evaluated using the setup involves the adsorption of CO_2 on commercial zeolites, calibration curves were also generated for CO_2 passing through the mixing box, as well as for CO_2 -He mixtures. These calibrations make it possible to determine the required valve opening percentages to produce a gas stream exiting the mixing box at 50 mL/min with a defined CO_2 concentration in helium.

Figure 26: Pure He Mass Flow Controller Calibration

Figure 27: Pure He from Gas Mixer Mass Flow Controller Calibration

Figure 28: Pure CO₂ from Gas Mixer Mass Flow Controller Calibration

The following mathematical development was considered for the calibration of the CO_2 -He mixture with a defined outlet composition and a total flow of 50 mL/min:

Mass Balance and Composition Definition in Volumetric Fraction

$$\dot{m}_{\text{mix}} = \dot{m}_{\text{He}} + \dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (4)$$

$$y_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{Q_{\text{CO}_2}}{Q_{\text{He}} + Q_{\text{CO}_2}} \quad (5)$$

Since the CO_2 -He system is considered approximately ideal under atmospheric pressure conditions according to [26], the following approximation can be made. However, if the system behaves non-ideally, an excess model should be used to predict V^E and calculate the respective Z value for each species:

$$\rho_{\text{mix}}Q_{\text{mix}} = \rho_{\text{He}}Q_{\text{He}} + \rho_{\text{CO}_2}Q_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (6)$$

Where Q_i is the volumetric flow rate of component i in (mL/min), and ρ_i is the density in (kg/mL). Assuming ideal gas behavior, the density is approximately linear with respect to temperature and pressure. However, to validate this assumption, the density of both components and the mixture was modeled using Peng-Robinson in Aspen Plus. It was found that He fits a linear trend more closely than CO_2 , which is consistent with the intermolecular interactions of each gas. The mixing temperature remained at ambient conditions, i.e., 18°C in Bogotá, and a pressure of 40 PSIG.

Figure 29: Pure CO_2 and He Density

The mixture density was then estimated as a function of CO_2 composition at the ambient temperature of Bogotá, resulting in the following plot:

Figure 30: CO_2 - He Mixture Density using Peng-Robinson at 18°C

It was found that a fifth-order polynomial regression resulted in errors

below 0.2%, while linear regression produced errors between 0.9% and 2.4%:

Figure 31: CO_2 - He Mixture Relative Error for lineal 5th order regression

With the densities of the pure components and the mixture calculated using the Peng-Robinson equation, and knowing that the desired total flow is 50 mL/min with a defined volumetric composition, the system of **Equations 5** and **6** allows determining the necessary flow rates of He and CO_2 to be introduced into the gas mixer. This results in a direct calibration curve for the percentage openings of both mass flow controllers:

$$y_{CO_2} = \frac{Q_{CO_2}}{Q_{He} + Q_{CO_2}}$$

$$Q_{CO_2} = y_{CO_2}(Q_{CO_2} + Q_{He})$$

$$Q_{He} = Q_{CO_2} \left(\frac{1}{y_{CO_2}} - 1 \right) \quad (7)$$

Substituting into Equation 6, we obtain:

$$Q_{He} = \frac{\rho_{\text{mix}} Q_{\text{mix}}}{\left(\frac{1}{y_{CO_2}} - 1\right) \rho_{He} + \rho_{CO_2}} \left(\frac{1}{y_{CO_2}} - 1\right) \quad (8)$$

Using the value of Q_{He} from Equation 7, Q_{CO_2} can be determined. With these values and the calibration curves, the corresponding opening percentages for each flow controller were obtained. The following results were observed:

Table 7: Comparison between theoretical and experimental flow rates for different CO₂/He mixtures

y_{CO_2} (vol/vol)	Q_{CO_2} (mL/min)	Q_{He} (mL/min)	%Area CO ₂	%Area He	Flow Rate Theoretical (cm ³ /min)	Flow Rate Experimental (cm ³ /min)	Relative Error (%)
0.05	2.5	47.1	12.4	82.7	50.00	50.34	0.67
0.10	4.9	44.5	24.7	78.0	50.00	49.93	0.13
0.15	7.4	41.9	37.0	73.5	50.00	50.13	0.25
0.20	9.8	39.4	49.2	69.1	50.00	50.19	0.37

This confirms that the linear adjustment of densities using the Peng-Robinson model consistently represents the CO₂-He mixture behavior. The final calibration curve to obtain a 50 mL/min gas mixture at 40 PSIG is shown below:

Figure 32: CO_2 - He Mixture Valve opening calibration to obtain 50 mL/min at 40 PSIG

2.3.4 TPD Experimentation Description

For this section, ammonium-form zeolite HY-type (Zeolyst CBV 100) will be used. This material will first undergo calcination in the U-shaped reactor, followed by either a TPD experiment or a study of diffusional phenomena through the injection of toluene and benzene probes into the zeolite. In both cases, the reactor is configured as follows:

Figure 33: U Reactor Arrangement

The reactor has a diameter of 1.5 cm and an approximate length of 30 cm. Inside, a zeolite layer with a thickness of 0.10 cm will be placed in its pure form, or 0.17 cm when diluted with silicon carbide at 4.5 wt%. This zeolite layer is supported by quartz wool, which provides mechanical stability and ensures that the bed remains in place. In addition, a 0.10 cm layer of ground quartz is included to improve temperature distribution within the reactor and to prevent the formation of hot spots, particularly during the calcination step. Lastly, a second layer of ground quartz is added to promote uniform gas flow through the bed and to avoid stagnation zones. This packed bed distribution, will have significant implications in Transport Phenomena along the TPD compared to the only Zeolite packed bed reactor.

A fixed bed was loaded with 60 ± 5 mg of sieved zeolite mixed with 1273 ± 5 mg of SiC, within the Mesh 140–200 range, corresponding to particle sizes of approximately 74 to 105 μm . The bed length was 1.7 ± 0.2 cm.

Adsorption of the probe molecule was carried out at three temperatures:

25°C, 75°C, and 150°C, based on the previous TPD results reported by [2]. Liquid pulses of 3, 4, or 6 μL of toluene and benzene were injected, rapidly evaporating into a 50 mL/min helium stream (inert carrier gas). Each pulse contained a known amount of the probe molecule, which was transported in vapor phase to the bed.

Saturation of the solid was considered to be achieved when the signals of successive pulses showed no significant differences in height or area, indicating that the solid could no longer adsorb additional amounts of the injected species. This method enabled controlled stepwise saturation and was preferred over direct saturation to improve resolution and control of the adsorbed amount, as mentioned in [2].

Once the bed was saturated, thermal desorption of the adsorbed species was performed starting in 298 K. The bed was heated up from there to 623 K at a linear rate of 10 K/min while maintaining a constant flow of helium. The desorption profile was recorded as a function of temperature, allowing analysis of the interaction strength between the probe molecule and the zeolite surface.

2.3.5 Mass Spectrometer Calibration

For the calibration of the Mass Spectrometer, the influence of the packed bed on the area under the peak curve at different temperatures was evaluated. To this end, 3 pulse injections of 3, 4, and 6 μL each were performed at three temperatures: 25, 75, and 150°C. The experiments were conducted using both an empty quartz reactor (Blank) and reactors packed with ground quartz and silicon carbide (SiC). The corresponding peak areas obtained from each experiment are presented in **Appendix B**. These areas were determined after smoothing the response curves using the Savitzky–Golay method, applying a stronger regression window in regions without peaks and a lighter one around the peak areas.

2.4 Results and Discussion

2.4.1 Mass Spectrometer Calibration Results

From the data obtained and presented in **Appendix B**, the following was found:

Table 8: Areas under the curve for Toluene pulses at different temperatures and packing materials (% Alkyl Aromatic · second)

Pulse (μL) T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3	4	6	Sample
25	338	466	795	Blank
25	456	659	943	SiC
75	231	329	497	Blank
75	369	474	723	SiC
150	327	433	713	Blank
150	395	510	766	SiC

Table 9: Areas under the curve for Benzene pulses at different temperatures and packing materials (% Alkyl Aromatic · second)

Pulse (μL) T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3	4	6	Sample
25	681	849	1225	Blank
25	1033	1265	1920	SiC
75	637	861	1208	Blank
75	768	920	1370	SiC
150	815	1002	1293	Blank
150	792	902	1254	SiC

When plotting the peak area as a function of the pulse size of the probe at the three temperatures, for both the blank tests and those with SiC (see **Appendix B.3**), a decreasing trend in peak area with increasing temperature is observed up to a certain point. Beyond that point, the peak area measured by the mass spectrometer increases again in the case of toluene. However, for benzene, the increase in peak area is only observed after 75°C , as shown in **Figure 34** and **Figure 38**:

Figure 34: Area under peaks (Blank sample) for a) Toluene and b) Benzene

Figure 35: Area under peaks (SiC sample) for a) Toluene and b) Benzene

In the case of Toluene, it is important to consider two key concepts: axial dispersion and transport restriction. The former is directly related to the gas density, while the latter depends on the medium through which the

gas flows. In this experiment, when the quartz differential reactor is empty, the observed peak area is lower compared to the case where the reactor is filled with a bed of ground quartz mixed with SiC, across all temperature ranges. This is attributed to the reduction of axial dispersion caused by flow restriction, which allows higher concentrations of Toluene to accumulate within the gas phase.

Additionally, a temperature-dependent trend is observed: at 25°C, the peak area is highest, both in the blank and with SiC ; it then decreases at 75°C and increases again at 150°C. To understand this behavior, two specific physical aspects of the system must be considered. First, since the injection is done by pulsing, Toluene enters as discrete droplets, which evaporate more or less rapidly depending on the temperature. Second, temperature also plays a direct role in the axial dispersion of the alkylaromatic compound. These two opposing factors produce the observed trend: at lower temperatures, the effect of lower gas density (which increases concentration) dominates; as temperature increases to 75°C, the higher density reduces concentration and thus peak area. However, once the boiling point of toluene (110.6°C) is surpassed, the effect of immediate evaporation becomes dominant. Therefore, at 150°C, although the gas density is higher, the rapid vaporization of the droplets results in significantly higher concentration and consequently, a larger peak area. This affirmation may be seen in **Appendix B.3**.

For the case of Benzene, the same relationship is observed: the peak area is greater with the SiC-packed bed compared to the empty reactor. On the other hand, in the empty reactor, there appears to be no significant difference between 25°C and 75°C due to density effects, likely because the boiling point of Benzene (80°C) is close to both temperatures. However, once the system reaches 150°C, Benzene undergoes rapid vaporization, causing a sudden increase in concentration, which in turn leads to a larger peak area. In the case of the packed bed, the structure appears to disperse the probe more effectively at 25°C, overcoming the effect of density and resulting in an increased peak area. However, at 75°C, the influence of density begins to play a more significant role.

2.4.2 Adsorption/Desorption Results

Based on the complete data available in **Appendix C**, and considering the experimental temperature ramp data from the reactor furnace, the following were obtained:

Figure 36: Benzene concentration and Temperature Ramp Results a) 25°C, b) 75°C and c) 150°C

Based on the previous plots, TPD graphs were finally obtained for each different Adsorption Temperature, as it may be seen in **Figure 39**:

Figure 37: Benzene TPD for Zeolite H-Y diluted in SiC

Regarding the peaks obtained in the Benzene TPD analysis, several key aspects must be considered to understand the physical phenomena occurring within the bed.

The first observation relates to the decrease in the intensity of the strong desorption peaks. This behavior is consistent with the fact that, as temperature increases, the kinetic energy of the molecules also increases. Consequently, their tendency to remain adsorbed on the surface decreases. Therefore, fewer molecules are adsorbed at higher temperatures compared to lower ones, which translates into smaller peaks on the desorption curve.

In addition, a slight shift in the peak temperature is observed as the adsorption temperature increases. This may be attributed to a reduction in molecule–molecule interactions, since a lower surface coverage allows molecules to access the stronger adsorption sites more easily, primarily due to reduced intermolecular interference.

Another notable observation is the appearance of a small desorption peak above 250°C, which is more pronounced for adsorption temperatures of

25°C and 75°C, but not for 150°C. This can be explained by considering the preferred state of benzene at each temperature. At 25°C and 75°C, adsorption is favored because benzene is not yet fully in the gaseous state, allowing more molecules to access hard-to-reach micropores and become adsorbed. In contrast, at 150°C—above benzene’s boiling point—the equilibrium favors the gas phase, reducing the extent of adsorption and thus resulting in a smaller desorption peak at higher temperature.

Moreover, due to the generally lower surface coverage at 150°C, stronger concentration gradients may develop. These gradients, during the cooling period down to 25°C, promote diffusion and redistribution of weakly adsorbed benzene molecules toward less occupied regions of the surface. This explains why, in the desorption curve corresponding to 150°C, desorption begins even before reaching the original adsorption temperature, and why a new desorption peak seems to emerge near the end of the curve.

Additionally, the subsequent section provides the TPD analysis results for Toluene:

Figure 38: Toluene concentration and Temperature Ramp Results a) 25°C, b) 75°C and c) 150°C

Figure 39: Benzene TPD for Zeolite H-Y diluted in SiC

These results reveal a similar trend, in which the peak amplitude decreases due to the system's tendency to remain adsorbed at lower temperatures. Additionally, the shift in peak position can be attributed to a reduced molecule–molecule interaction within the pore network, considering that as the adsorption temperature increases, the population of adsorbed molecules decreases, thus favoring desorption.

Moreover, when compared to the Benzene results, it becomes evident that the TPD profiles for Toluene exhibit peaks with pseudo-peaks (shoulders), particularly noticeable at 25°C and 75°C, whereas such features are absent in the Benzene profiles. This difference may be directly related to molecular size: since Toluene has a larger molecular size than Benzene, it is more likely to experience diffusional limitations, which may give rise to these pseudo-peaks. Furthermore, a significant increase in the desorption temperature is observed between the two compounds. While Benzene desorbs completely between 255–295°C, Toluene does so between 305–425°C, depending on the adsorption temperature. This also explains the absence of an additional desorption peak for Toluene, unlike Benzene. Although higher temperatures

favor desorption and generate a favorable concentration gradient (due to lower surface coverage), diffusion into micropores is still hindered in the case of Toluene, given its larger molecular size compared to Benzene.

Finally, in order to obtain a first qualitative estimate of the number of predominant adsorption sites in each of the TPD profiles, a Gaussian convolution fitting was performed using the `lsqcurvefit` optimization function in MATLAB. The number of peaks was user-defined, and the algorithm adjusted the parameters to minimize the error between the experimental TPD curve and the fitted model. The equation used for the convolution was:

$$y(T) = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(T - \mu_i)^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right)$$

where:

- $y(T)$ is the desorbed signal (intensity) at temperature T ,
- A_i is the amplitude of the i -th Gaussian peak,
- μ_i is the center (temperature of maximum desorption) of the i -th peak,
- σ_i is the standard deviation of the i -th peak,
- and n is the total number of Gaussian peaks used in the fit.

Obtaining for Benzene:

Figure 40: Benzene TPD Gaussian Convolution 25°C n=5

Figure 41: Benzene TPD Gaussian Convolution 75°C n=4

Figure 42: Benzene TPD Gaussian Convolution 150°C n=3

And for Toluene:

Figure 43: Toluene TPD Gaussian Convolution 25°C n=4

Figure 44: Toluene TPD Gaussian Convolution 75°C n=5

Figure 45: Toluene TPD Gaussian Convolution 150°C n=3

From there, the following Tables were tabulated:

Furthermore, as a final comment in this section, there is a significant difference compared to the data obtained in the thesis by [2], in which a greater number of diffusional limitations can be observed for the H-Y Zeolite

T (°C)	n	A	μ	σ
25	1	0.29	46.45	9.15
	2	1.91	131.13	31.20
	3	4.22	234.73	19.15
	4	3.98	202.47	26.78
	5	0.45	330.40	14.12
75	1	2.13	138.59	30.70
	2	3.89	193.68	21.26
	3	2.68	218.56	15.72
	4	0.40	306.20	14.57
150	1	0.46	99.03	27.05
	2	2.28	181.58	27.26
	3	2.77	213.47	19.72
	4	0.13	310.47	12.73

Table 10: Fitted parameters from Gaussian convolution of Benzene TPD curves at different adsorption temperatures.

T (°C)	n	A	μ	σ
25	1	0.70	101.25	20.40
	2	4.33	223.87	49.65
	3	6.32	301.49	34.60
	4	0.19	405.08	10.47
75	1	0.26	102.17	17.15
	2	3.81	275.44	28.79
	3	2.69	209.40	45.06
	4	0.08	373.07	10.99
	5	0.08	425.14	6.75
150	1	0.0001	99.0421	0.0343
	2	1.1727	253.8591	19.8697
	3	2.1445	211.2541	29.8077

Table 11: Fitted parameters from Gaussian convolution of Toluene TPD curves at different adsorption temperatures.

CBV 100, as shown below in Figure 46:

Figure 46: Toluene and Benzene TPD reported by [2] at 25°C as Adsorption Temperature

The above comparison with the results obtained in the present thesis is consistent, considering that in Cindy Ly's experiments, the zeolite bed was not diluted with SiC. This hinders the transport of alkyl aromatics through the bed, resulting in broader TPD profiles that reach significantly higher temperatures than those observed in the present work. In contrast, in this thesis, the cavities formed due to the grain size of the SiC promote enhanced mobility, facilitating transport compared to the undiluted bed experiments.

2.5 Conclusions

Based on the results obtained in this section, clear differences were observed in the TPD desorption profiles between benzene and toluene, which are mainly attributed to molecular size and diffusional limitations within the porous structure of the H-Y zeolite CBV 100. Benzene exhibited more defined curves, with well-separated peaks and no shoulders, indicating a desorption process less limited by diffusional phenomena. In contrast, toluene showed peaks with pseudo-peaks (shoulders), especially at adsorption temperatures of 25°C and 75°C, suggesting greater difficulty in the adsorption-desorption

processes due to internal diffusion barriers and a greater diversity of adsorption sites.

When analyzing the effects of adsorption temperature, it was found that the desorption peaks tend to shift toward lower temperatures as the adsorption temperature increases. This behavior can be explained by a lower population of adsorbed molecules, which reduces cooperative interactions and favors earlier desorption. Moreover, the intensity of the peaks was found to decrease significantly as the adsorption temperature increased, indicating that the system tends to remain in the adsorbed state for a shorter time due to the higher kinetic energy of the alkyl aromatic molecules. In the case of benzene, new higher-energy peaks appeared when the adsorption temperatures were higher, which may be understood as the result of weaker interactions with neighboring adsorbed molecules and increased kinetic energy that allows access to micropores that were previously inaccessible.

The application of the Gaussian convolution model allowed only for a qualitative (not phenomenological) characterization and identification of the predominant adsorption sites. However, it remains necessary to apply a phenomenological model capable of adequately predicting the observed adsorption–desorption behaviors.

Finally, when comparing the results of this thesis with those obtained in Cindy Ly's thesis, it was found that the absence of SiC dilution in her experimental setup led to greater restrictions in molecular mobility within the system, resulting in broader TPD profiles and significantly higher maximum desorption temperatures. In contrast, the use of a SiC-diluted bed in this work enhanced the diffusion of aromatic compounds through the bed, reducing transport limitations and clarifying more precisely the restrictive effects of adsorption–desorption in the H-Y zeolite CBV 100, particularly with respect to the influence of bed configuration (dilution).

References

- [1] N. V. Vlasenko, Y. N. Kochkin, G. M. Telbiz, O. V. Shvets, and P. E. Strizhak, “Insight into the active site nature of zeolite h-bea for liquid phase etherification of isobutylene with ethanol,” *Reaction Chemistry & Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1356–1366, 2023.
- [2] C. L. T. Méndez, “Evaluación de las propiedades texturales y de transporte difusivo de zeolitas y mesoestructuradas sobre el comportamiento catalítico en una reacción de ruptura,” Tesis de Maestría, Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Bogotá, Colombia, 2020, facultad de Ciencias, Departamento de Química.
- [3] X. Guo, L. Guo, Y. Zeng, R. Kosol, X. Gao, Y. Yoneyama, G. Yang, and N. T. , *Catalytic oligomerization of isobutyl alcohol to jet fuels over dealuminated zeolite Beta*. Elsevier Ltd, 2021.
- [4] T. Yoshioka, R. Ohnishi, T. Hirose, Y. Kamimura, H. Okubo, Y. Kuroda, Y. Kuroda, Y. K. Takahashi, R. A. Sasaki, M. Takata, Y. Wakihara, and M. Takata, “Dealumination of small-pore zeolites through pore-opening migration process with the aid of pore-filler stabilization,” *Science Advances*, vol. 8, no. 25, p. eabo3093, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.abo3093>
- [5] A. Corma, J. Pérez-Pariente, and C. Martínez, “Structure and catalytic behavior of beta zeolite,” *Journal of Catalysis*, vol. 148, no. 2, pp. 569–574, 1994.
- [6] A. Corma, “State of the art and future challenges of zeolites as catalysts,” *Journal of Catalysis*, vol. 216, no. 1–2, pp. 298–312, 2003.
- [7] S. I. Zones, “Conversion of faujasite to high silica zeolite beta via seeding,” *Journal of the Chemical Society, Faraday Transactions*, vol. 87, no. 24, pp. 3709–3716, 1991.
- [8] T. F. D. Jr., “The implications of the discovery of zeolite beta,” *Micro-porous and Mesoporous Materials*, vol. 35–36, pp. 245–252, 2000.
- [9] R. M. Barrer, *Hydrothermal Chemistry of Zeolites*. Academic Press, 1982.

- [10] J. Weitkamp, “Zeolites and catalysis,” *Solid State Ionics*, vol. 131, no. 1–2, pp. 175–188, 2000.
- [11] Y. Fan, X. Bao, X. Lin, G. Shi, and H. Liu, “Acidity adjustment of hzsm-5 zeolites by dealumination and realumination with steaming and citric acid treatments,” *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, vol. 110, no. 31, pp. 15 411–15 416, 2006.
- [12] J. Pérez-Ramírez, C. Christensen, K. Johannsen, and I. Schmidt, “Hierarchical zeolites: Enhanced molecular diffusion and catalysis of alkylaromatics,” *Catalysis Today*, vol. 82, pp. 145–154, 2003.
- [13] M. Haouas, F. Taulelle, and J. Sommer, “Recent advances in understanding the structure and dynamics of zeolite catalysts by solid-state nmr,” *Chemical Society Reviews*, vol. 37, pp. 1116–1130, 2008.
- [14] Y. Li and J. Yu, “New stories of zeolite structures: their descriptions, determinations, predictions, and evaluations,” *Chemical Reviews*, vol. 114, no. 14, pp. 7268–7316, 2016.
- [15] T. Nguyen and E. Iglesia, “Transport phenomena in packed beds of zeolite crystals: effects of porosity and crystal size on the tpd profiles of alkanes and aromatics,” *Journal of Catalysis*, vol. 323, pp. 34–46, 2015.
- [16] E. Hernández-Maldonado and R. Yang, “Desorption kinetics and diffusional limitations in temperature-programmed desorption of volatile organic compounds in zeolites,” *Industrial Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 42, no. 13, pp. 3103–3112, 2003.
- [17] T. Yokoi, K. Mochizuki, and T. Tatsumi, “Design of mesostructured zeolites with improved accessibility and catalytic performance,” *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, vol. 280, pp. 203–211, 2019.
- [18] Zeolyst International, “Safety data sheet: Zeolite cbv100 powder (nay),” 2023, available at: <https://www.zeolyst.com/products/hy-zeolite-cbv100>.
- [19] D. W. Breck, *Zeolite Molecular Sieves: Structure, Chemistry, and Use*. New York: Wiley-Interscience, 1974.

- [20] M. Nichterwitz, M. Borchardt, and T. Thielmann, “Solvent-free hierarchization of zeolites by carbochlorination,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, vol. 5, pp. 221–229, 2017.
- [21] Zeolyst International, “Product information: Zeolite hy cbv100,” 2022, available at: <https://www.knowde.com/stores/zeolyst-international/products/cbv-100>.
- [22] C. Blazek, A. Klamt, and R. Gläser, “Catalytic cracking of polymers over zeolites: Effect of acidity and pore size,” *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, vol. 94, no. 1-3, pp. 129–138, 2006.
- [23] A. Rodriguez and L. Peña, “Textural properties and structural behavior of zeolyst nay cbv100,” SSRN Electronic Journal, 2023, available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4134264>.
- [24] S. Turner, M. J. Hudson, and J. Klinowski, “Characterization of zeolite y as a reference material for industrial applications,” *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, vol. 103, no. 1–3, pp. 219–226, 2007.
- [25] D. Garcia, E. Martinez, and J. Lopez, “Ammonia-scr performance of cu/hy zeolites derived from cbv100 under flue-gas conditions,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 401–409, 2024.
- [26] J. Dávila, Z. E. Heinemann, and M. Kribernegg, “Accurate calculations of compressibility factor for pure gases and gas mixtures,” in *Proceedings of the 5th European Conference on the Mathematics of Oil Recovery*, Leoben, Austria, Sep. 1996, pp. –, experimental values of Z for CO_2 and He at 295 K.

APPENDICES

A Standard Operating Procedure's (SOP's)

This section includes the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for the operation of the Mass Spectrometer and the execution of the adsorption and desorption runs in the quartz differential reactor, developed in this thesis.

A.1 Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) - Differential Reactor Operation

1. Check that all plugs are connected to their respective controllers (Box, He/Ar, and Valve 1) and to their power sources.
2. Turn on the heating tapes with the controllers and set the set point to preheat the gas.
3. Turn on the furnace and program the corresponding temperature ramps according to the following protocol:
 - a. Press the up and down arrows simultaneously. Use `Mode` to go to `Global` and check that `RATE` is in `Ptyp`. Press `DSPY`.
 - b. Program the ramp: Press `Mode`, then use the up arrow to go to `Prog`, select `File 1` with `Mode`, then step 1 with `Mode`, `Mode` (enter set point), `Mode` (input desired set point value), `Mode` (set the heating rate in $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), `Mode` to go to `File 1, step 2`, and set `SOAH` to maintain temperature for x hours, y minutes, z seconds.
 - c. Once the heating ramp is programmed, turn on the furnace using `Hold/Run` (hold and select the file you want to activate).
 - d. Ensure the furnace controller switch is pointing upwards.

Note: It is important to heat slowly, with a maximum rate of $1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, as overshooting the set point is possible due to the furnace's electric power.

4. Once the furnace is on, open the valves of the gases to be used to 40 psi.

5. Turn on the mass flow controllers and set the flows according to the respective calibration curves.
6. Set valves V1 and V2 so that there is gas flow to the QGA (Mass Spectrometer).

Note: The three-way valve at the outlet of V2 must be open, either for the gas from the valve array or atmospheric gas.

7. Turn on the mass spectrometer:
 - a. Check that the QGA and computer plugs are connected.
 - b. Turn on the computer.
 - c. Verify gas flow to the chromatograph.
 - d. Turn on the QGA (green button on the back of the equipment).
 - e. Press the button twice.
 - f. Press the button again.
 - g. Press the down arrow twice.
 - h. Wait until the pressure reads 5.0×10^{-6} .
 - i. Press the green button on the lower left corner on the front panel (check that one of the filament buttons turns on).
 - j. Open Massoft and open a test case to activate the system.
 - k. Open the Hidden QGA program.
 - l. Load **Analysis**.
 - m. Connect.
 - n. Start.

During online analysis with the mass spectrometer, turn off axis 3 and axis 2.

8. Once the data have been taken and saved, shut down the equipment:
 - a. Click **Stop** in Hidden QGA.
 - b. Click **Exit**.
 - c. Disconnect.

- d. Click Shut Down.
 - e. Wait 10 minutes.
 - f. Turn off the mass spectrometer (green switch, bottom left).
 - g. Press the button once.
 - h. Press the up arrow once.
 - i. Press the button twice.
 - j. Once the pump has turned off, turn off the back switch.
9. Turn off the heating tape controllers.
 10. Close the mass flow controller valves from the controller.
 11. Turn off the mass flow controllers.
 12. Close the gas lines in Instrumental 1 and the cylinders next to the Filtration equipment.

A.2 Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) - Adsorption/Desorption

1. Load the quartz reactor with zeolite placed between layers of ground quartz and SiC in the desired amounts. Carefully mount the reactor along with the plastic airtight seals (o-rings) into the gas inlet and outlet ports respectively. Tighten the nuts using the provided wrenches.
2. Check for leaks at the nut coupling region using a soap solution.
3. Turn on the helium (He) flow to remove atmospheric air from the system. Once the mass spectrometer no longer detects air, switch to ultra-dry air at 50 mL/min.
4. Program the calcination ramp in the furnace to 1–2°C/min until reaching 450°C, so that calcination takes about 5 to 7 hours. Then hold at 450°C for 2 hours. (It is recommended to leave it overnight with a constant flow of dry air.)
5. Switch valve 1 to pure He flow (50 mL/min) until all dry air is displaced.
6. Program the adsorption temperature.

7. Saturate the bed with the selected probe, either by pulses or continuously.
8. Program the desorption ramp to $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 350°C and execute it to obtain the desorption curve.
9. Disassemble and remove the sample, or calcine again with H_2 to regenerate the zeolite and reuse it (restart from step 1).

B Mass Spectrometer Calibration Results

B.1 Smoothed Results for Mass Spectrometer Calibration

Figure 47: Smoothed Toluene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)

Figure 48: Smoothed Toluene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)

Figure 49: Smoothed Toluene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)

Figure 50: Smoothed Benzene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)

Figure 51: Smoothed Benzene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)

Figure 52: Smoothed Benzene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)

Figure 53: Smoothed Toluene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)

Figure 54: Smoothed Toluene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)

Figure 55: Smoothed Toluene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)

Figure 56: Smoothed Benzene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)

Figure 57: Smoothed Benzene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)

Figure 58: Smoothed Benzene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)

B.2 Area under smoothed peaks for Mass Spectrometer Calibration

Figure 59: Area under Toluene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)

Figure 60: Area under Toluene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)

Figure 61: Area under Toluene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)

Figure 62: Area under Benzene peaks at 25°C (Blank sample)

Figure 63: Area under Benzene peaks at 75°C (Blank sample)

Figure 64: Area under Benzene peaks at 150°C (Blank sample)

Figure 65: Area under Toluene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)

Figure 66: Area under Toluene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)

Figure 67: Area under Toluene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)

Figure 68: Area under Benzene peaks at 25°C (SiC sample)

Figure 69: Area under Benzene peaks at 75°C (SiC sample)

Figure 70: Area under Benzene peaks at 150°C (SiC sample)

B.3 Results of Probe Injection Tests in the Differential Reactor: Empty and with a Bed of Ground Quartz and SiC

Figure 71: Area under peaks as function of Temperature in (Blank sample)
a) Toluene b) Benzene

Figure 72: Area under peaks as function of Temperature in (SiC sample) a) Toluene b) Benzene

Figure 73: Area under peaks as function of Toluene 25°C pulse volume, comparison between Blank and SiC

Figure 74: Area under peaks as function of Toluene 75°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC

Figure 75: Area under peaks as function of Toluene 150°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC

Figure 76: Area under peaks as function of Benzene 25°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC

Figure 77: Area under peaks as function of Benzene 75°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC

Figure 78: Area under peaks as function of Benzene 150°C pulse volume, comparison between Blanck and SiC

C Saturation peaks and TPD Results

The following section presents benzene pulse injections equivalent to $3\mu\text{L}$ each, continued until saturation was reached, and subsequently used for saturation analysis. The Savitzky-Golay method was employed for data smoothing.

Figure 79: Benzene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at $25^{\circ}C$ followed by TPD analysis.

Figure 80: Benzene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at $75^{\circ}C$ followed by TPD analysis.

Figure 81: Benzene 25°C Adsorption TPD

Figure 82: Benzene 75°C Adsorption TPD

Figure 83: Benzene 150°C Adsorption TPD

Figure 84: Toluene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at 25°C followed by TPD analysis.

Figure 85: Toluene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at $75^{\circ}C$ followed by TPD analysis.

Figure 86: Toluene injection in $3\mu L$ pulses at $150^{\circ}C$ followed by TPD analysis.

Figure 87: Toluene 25°C Adsorption TPD

Figure 88: Toluene 75°C Adsorption TPD

Figure 89: Toluene 150°C Adsorption TPD